

LEVEL OF EMOTIONAL MATURITY AMONG THE WOMEN STUDENTS OF PROFESSIONAL AND NON-PROFESSIONAL COLLEGES

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Abstract

Research Background: Emotions play an important role in life and contribute to the personal and social development of an individual. Continuous emotional disturbance affects the individual growth and development and gives rise to mental, physical, social and other problems. On the other hand, an emotionally stable individual leads a happy, healthy and peaceful life.

Research Objectives: The study objective was, to study the significant difference in level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges. Other objective was, to study the significant difference in level of emotional maturity among the women students of urban and rural.

Research Methods: The study one hundred twenty women students were selected from different professional and non-professional colleges in the district of Pune. Their age range was between 18 to 19 years. The study purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the sample. The study Emotional Maturity scale developed by Dr. Mahesh Bhargava has been used for data collection.

Conclusions: It is concluded that, insignificant difference found in level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional college as well as urban and rural women students. There is no significant interaction found among type of colleges and type of region in terms of their level of emotional maturity.

Implementations: The study will be helpful and beneficial to understand the significant difference in the level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges.

Keywords- Emotional Maturity, Women Students, Professional & Non-Professional Colleges

INTRODUCTION

One outcome of healthy emotional development is increasing "Emotional Maturity". Emotional maturity should be regarded as relative, not final or absolute. The process of maturity emotionally is never complete, for a person in fairly good health mentally continues to grow more "mauler" According to Walter D. Smitson (1974), "Emotional maturity is a process in which the personality is continuously striving for greater sense of emotional health, both intra-physically and interpersonally." According to Rather T. Jerkily, "emotional maturity means the degree to which the

person has realized his potential for richness of living and has developed his capacity to enjoy things, to relate himself to others, to love and to laugh," to feel sorrow at the time of grief, to be frightened, without wearing any mask. According to Crow and Crow (1974), "An emotion is an affective experience that accompanies generalizes inner adjustment and mental and psychologically stirred up states in an individual and that shows itself in his overt behavior."

Emotions play an important role in life and contribute to the personal and social development of an individual. Continuous emotional disturbance affects the individual growth and development and gives rise to mental, physical, social and other problems. It hampers intellectual training. On the other hand, an emotionally stable individual leads a happy, healthy and peaceful life. He is at ease with himself, his surroundings and other fellow beings. Emotional maturity is the result of healthy emotional development. The emotional mature person is able to hide his feelings; such a person is not subject to swings in mood and can suffer in silence. When he does express emotions, he does so with moderation, decently, and in good order. Emotional maturity is having proper emotion at proper time and to express it in proper form and in proper quality. Emotional maturity is an effective determinant to shaping the personality, attitudes and behavior of the youth into accepting responsibility, making decision, teaming with group, developing healthy relationship and enhancing self-worth.

The present study objective was forced to study the significant difference in level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges as well as urban and rural. The study will be helpful and beneficial to understand the significant difference in the level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges. As well as the present study will be beneficial to educationalists, psychologists, counselors, teachers for understanding the level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To compare and analyzed the significant difference in the level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges.
2. To study the significant difference in level of emotional maturity among the women students of urban and rural.
3. To study the significant interaction among the effects of type of college and type of region on emotional maturity.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. There will have no significant difference in the level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges.
2. There will have no significant difference in level of emotional maturity among the women students of urban and rural.
3. There will have no significant interaction among the effects of type of college and type of region on emotional maturity.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable
<p>Type of College:</p> <p>A. Professional College Women</p> <p>B. Non-Professional College Women</p> <p>Type of Region</p> <p>A. Urban Women Students</p> <p>B. Rural Women Students</p>	Emotional Maturity

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The study one hundred twenty women students were selected from different professional and non-professional colleges in the district of Pune. Out of sample, 60 (30 Urban and 30 Rural) women were selected from professional colleges and same way, 60 (30 Urban and 30 Rural) women were selected from non-professional colleges. Their age range was between 18 to 19 years. The study purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the sample.

MATERIALS OF THE STUDY

- **Emotional Maturity scale:**

Emotional Maturity Scale developed by Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava (2005) has been used in the present study. The reliability of the test by product moment correlation was 0.75. The internal consistency for emotional stability was 0.75, emotional progression was 0.63, social adjustment was 0.58, personality integration was 0.86 and independence was 0.42 respectively and the concurrent validity of the total test was 0.64 as given in the manual.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table No. 1. Assessing normality of dependent variable emotional maturity

Descriptive Statistics		Statistic	Std. Error	
Emotional Maturity	Mean	66.075	0.97462	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	64.145	
		Upper Bound	68.004	
	5% Trimmed Mean	65.916		
	Median	67.000		
	Variance	113.986		
	Std. Deviation	10.676		
	Minimum	36.00		
	Maximum	91.00		
	Range	55.00		
	Interquartile Range	16.00		
	Skewness	0.179	0.221	
	Kurtosis	0.276	0.438	

Above table indicates that the trimmed mean score (65.916) is very close to simple mean (66.075) of women students of college on their emotional maturity. Hence, we confidently explain that our simple mean is not affected extreme scores, and indicates that there is not a single outlier in our data (Sheridan, J. Coakes, 2006). The Skewness and kurtosis both scores are Positive. The positive values for Skewness indicate a positive skew, while positive values for kurtosis indicate a distribution that is peaked.

Graph No:1: Shown normality of dependent variable emotional maturity.

Table No. 2. Descriptive statistics of dependent variable emotional Maturity

Dependent Variable: Emotional Maturity				
Types of Colleges	Types of Region	Mean	S. D.	N
Professional College Women	Urban Women Students	64.900	11.216	30
	Rural Women Students	65.700	7.688	30
	Total	65.300	9.542	60
Non-Professional College Women	Urban Women Students	66.400	12.107	30
	Rural Women Students	67.300	11.531	30
	Total	66.850	11.731	60
Total	Urban Women Students	65.650	11.596	60
	Rural Women Students	66.500	9.750	60
	Total	66.075	10.676	120

Table: Summary of ANOVA of the dependent variable emotional Maturity

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Type of Colleges	72.075	1	72.075	0.621	NS	0.005
Type of Region	21.675	1	21.675	0.187	NS	0.002
Type of Colleges X Type of Region	0.075	1	0.075	0.001	NS	0.000
Error	13470.500	116	116.125			
Total	537473.000	120				
Corrected Total	13564.325	119				

Significant Level, $df(1,116) \text{ ---- } 0.05 = 3.92 \quad 0.01 = 6.84$

The above table indicates a two-way ANOVA was conducted that examined the effect of type of college and region on individual's level of emotional maturity. Our dependent variable, emotional maturity, was normally distributed for the groups formed by the combination of the type of college and region.

The main effects analysis showed that for type of college is not significant, $F(1,116) = 0.621$, $P > 0.05$. There is no significant difference found in level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges. The women students of professional colleges and women students of professional colleges have been found equal on their emotional maturity. So, hypothesis no.1: is accepted.

The main effects analysis showed that for type of region is not significant, $F(1,116) = 0.187$, $P > 0.05$. There is insignificant difference found in level of emotional maturity among the women students of urban and rural. The women students of urban and women students of rural have been found equal on their emotional maturity. So, hypothesis no.2: is accepted.

There is insignificant interaction between the effects of type of college and region on individuals level of emotional maturity, $F(1,116) = 0.001$, $P > 0.05$. There is no significant interaction found among type of colleges and type of region in terms of their level of emotional maturity. So, hypothesis no.3: is accepted. Therefore, insignificantly influences found type of college and region on level of emotional maturity of professional and non-professional college's women students.

CONCLUSIONS

1. There is no significant difference found in level of emotional maturity among the women students of professional and non-professional colleges. The women students of professional colleges and women students of professional colleges have been found equal on their emotional maturity.

2. There is insignificant difference found in level of emotional maturity among the women students of urban and rural. The women students of urban and women students of rural have been found equal on their emotional maturity.
3. There is no significant interaction found among type of colleges and type of region in terms of their level of emotional maturity. Therefore, insignificantly influences found type of college and region on level of emotional maturity of professional and non-professional colleges' women students.

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